

Controlling electrical measurement devices with cloud integration

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Abstract. In industries, generating plants with renewable energies, etc., there are a multitude of electrical variable measurement equipment with communication capabilities through different buses such as TCP/IP and RS485 that support the communication protocol with Modbus equipment. For both existing and newly implemented installations, having real-time measurement data in the cloud to be viewed or processed is essential in today's electrical installations. The use of wired technologies would increase the cost of this implementation. Wireless technologies make it easy, reduce the cost, and are ideal for these types of tasks. This research aims to develop equipment that connects to meters, extracts the information and sends it to the cloud in real time.

Keywords: LPWAN, LoRa, Cloud Computing.

1 Introduction

A multitude of metering devices are installed to monitor installations that only provide data locally. The same is often true for new installations. On the other hand, most of the new installations are not monitored either. The vast majority of these devices have Modbus interfaces, under RS485 or TCP/IP protocol, which enables access to data and programming of the devices.

Access to the devices is wired, which would imply a large outlay for both new and existing installations, with the installation of a large amount of wiring, which would make this installation unfeasible.

Measuring devices are also often far away from the control areas, or are installed in areas that are difficult to access, or in environments that are harmful to people. This is where wireless technologies find their niche application.

Traditional Bluetooth technology does not make much sense in these installations, as its range of action is small, and it would not change much from a traditional inspection by looking directly at the reading of the device. Wi-Fi (Wireless-Fidelity) technology is very applicable in this type of application, but has several drawbacks. The first

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of these is its radius of action, which although it is greater than Bluetooth requires routers or signal repeaters to increase coverage in large areas such as industrial areas. Secondly, it is vulnerable to external attacks that could hack into the system.

This is where LPWAN (Low-Power Wide Area Wireless Network) technologies have their application. In this research, the LoRa (Long-Range) network has been chosen with coverage ratios of 5-10 km and more than 1000 devices per concentrator that make them sufficient for industrial installations from small to large.

Cloud computing is fundamental nowadays, that is why the devices created in this research send information in real time to the cloud so that the data can be visualized and analysed in real time.

2 Related Work

Before starting with the development of the equipment, it is necessary to review the state of the art in the monitoring of electrical installations, with emphasis on those that use IoT (Internet of Things) access and wireless communications.

Cano-Ortega et al. [1] realized a device to monitor the efficiency and operating conditions of induction motors in industrial environments using LoRa technology. Abete et al. [2] implemented a low-cost IoT connected meter based on the ADE7913 measurement chip. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [3] developed a control and measurement system for public lighting networks based on a LoRa network. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [4] built an energy efficiency system for public lighting under a LoRa LPWAN network. Francisco Sánchez-Sutil et al. [5] designed and tested a control and data reading device for power quality analyzers using ModBus and RS485 communication, eliminating wiring and using a wireless LoRa LPWAN network. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [6] implemented a Smart plug to monitor and control electrical devices in homes with LoRa communication. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [7] developed an energy efficiency system for irrigation systems using LoRaWAN. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [8] designed and implemented a real-time smart meter with LoRa communication. Cano-Ortega et al. [9] built a smart meter for residential environments with application of TLBO algorithm and LoRaWAN networks. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [10] developed a power quality analyzer for monitoring public lighting networks with LoRa wireless communication system.

The most widely used technology in IoT devices for monitoring electrical installations is Wi-Fi (Wireless-Fidelity), and there are several articles that describe devices that send information using this technology. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [11] developed a low-cost, open-source home meter for homes with PV installations. Medeiros et al. [12] implemented a three-phase metering device using Wi-Fi and low cost, to be installed in homes and industrial environments. Hernández et al. [13] studied the influence of data sampling frequency in electrical installations, with case studies in Spain, using Smart Meters with Wi-Fi technology. Hlaing et al. [14] built a Smart Meter with Wi-Fi and IoT connection for single-phase installations. Cano-Ortega et al. [15] developed a platform to analyze large amounts of data in the cloud from measurements in homes, PV

plants and electric vehicle chargers. Salor et al. [16] implemented a mobile power quality meter for transmission facilities. Benavides et al. [17] developed a model to remotely control a microgrid based on demand-side power control.

3 Hardware design

Measuring equipment is usually installed in electrical panels where there is not much space for the placement of the device designed in this research. It is therefore necessary to design a PCB (Printed Control Board) as small as possible. For this purpose, components of reduced dimensions have been chosen. The device has been designed to work with Wi-Fi and/or LoRa at the same time. However, it is possible to design smaller boards with only one of the two wireless networks.

One of the small, versatile and powerful microcontrollers available on the market is the Arduino Nano (AN) [18], which is why it has been chosen for this research. Following the criteria of miniaturization, the Wemos d1 mini (Wd1m) [19] microcontroller with Wi-Fi network access has been chosen, which works with an ESP8266 compatible chip. W1dm allows access to the cloud using Google's Firebase service [20]. W1dm has a Deek-Robot ID8122 datalogger connected to it to time the measurements in real time, it also has a microSD card slot available which could optionally save the data locally. For the LoRa network, a Dragino LA66 LoRaWAN shield [21] (LA66S) chip has been chosen. The test devices are five Carlo Gavazzi EM24DINAV93XISX [22] devices for monitoring the AC side of the inverter and the public grid, one VMUM4AS1T2XT [23] device, one VMUSAV30XSXX [24] device and one VMUP2TIWXSX [25] device. VMUM4AS1T2XT interfaces to the ModBus network for VMUSAV30XSXX and a VMUP2TIWXSX device. Therefore, there are three devices connected to the ModBus network.

Access to Firebase from the LoRa network is not direct, but requires the node network service as a gateway. LA66S sends the data to the PG1302 hub [26]. This hub sends the data to TTN (The Things Network) via a wired or Wi-Fi Internet connection, which is already installed on a Raspberry Pi 4 [27]. TTN has implemented a server with MQTT protocol (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) [28] for each project, this server is connected to Node-Red, which in turn sends it to Firebase. The applications for mobile devices are enhanced with MIT App Inventor [29]. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of the device.

Fig. 3. Assembled PCB board of the control access to measurement devices.

4 Software design

4.1 AN Nano programming

AN performs the data acquisition process by connecting via RS485 and ModBus with the measurement devices, implemented by the manufacturer of these devices. The program must initialize (i) the serial communications port to connect to XY-R485; (ii) the virtual serial port to communicate with W1dm; (iii) the XY-R485 module. Once the initialization is done, it must continuously read the virtual serial port, if a measurement command arrives, send the measurement order to XY-R485 through the serial port, and once the data is received, send it through the virtual serial port to W1dm. Fig. 4 shows the AN flow diagram.

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Fig. 4. AN main flow chart.

4.2 W1dm programming

W1dm is responsible for the operation of the device. It must first start (i) the real-time clock; (ii) the serial port for communication with AN; (iii) the virtual serial port for communication with LA66S; (iv) the Wi-Fi adapter. Continuously, W1dm should send measurement commands to AN, once the measurement data is received take the real-time clock time, upload the data to Firebase using the Wi-Fi connection and send the data to LA66S for uploading to the LoRa network. Fig. 5 shows the flowchart of W1dm

Fig. 5. W1dm main flow chart.

4.3 Programming Node-Network

The LoRa network cannot connect directly to Firebase to have the data in the cloud, but it is sent directly to TTN which implements an MQTT server for each device. To connect TTN with Firebase, Node-Red is used as a gateway. For this purpose Node-Red waits for an event from TTN, collects and converts the necessary data and sends it to Firebase. In addition to the electrical data, the LoRa network parameters are also collected for communication statistics and to improve the network. Fig. 6 shows part of the Node-Red program, corresponding to the LoRa system variables.

Fig. 6. Node-Red program.

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4.4 Programming for data download

Firebase can store up to 1 GB free of charge. Therefore, the information is downloaded daily and saved for historical purposes. In this sense, a Python program has been created that connects to each Firebase project, unloads the information that exists up to the day before the current one and deletes the information once it has been downloaded. To do this, the program has been included in the Windows task manager so that it runs at 2 am daily. Fig. 7 show the flowchart.

Fig. 7. Download data flow chart.

5 Results

5.1 Test equipment

To perform the tests, the PV installation of the Department of Electrical Engineering of the University of Jaén has been used. The installation is located on the terrace of the A3 building of the Campus de las Lagunillas in Jaén. The installation consists of 10 Axitec model AC-270P/156-60 panels providing 2.97 kWp, connected to a grid-connected SMA Sunny boy 3000 TL-21 inverter, located in the A3-265 laboratory. On the terrace together with the PV panels are installed the modules VMUM4AS1T2XT, VMUSAV30XSXX and VMUP2TIWXSX. In the laboratory, next to the inverter there are 2 modules EM24DINAV93XISX to monitor the AC side of the inverter and the public grid. Fig. 8 shows the installation for carrying out the tests.

Fig. 8. (a) Arrangement of the solar panels; (b) switchboard located on the terrace of building A3; (c) switchboard located in the laboratory A3-265.

5.2 Data obtained

The information generated can be used for analysis and representation, which can be used to make improvements to the installation. The data is downloaded daily at 2 am and saved in csv format,

The data shown in Fig. 9 for the DC side and Fig. 10 for the AC side were recorded on 7 July 2024. Part (a) shows the voltage decaying to 0 VDC when there is no sun, and remaining around 300 VDC during generation hours. As for the DC currents they are shown in part (b) which have a maximum at around 8.5 ADC. In consonance with the current, the DC power is shown in part (c), which has a maximum value of around 2.5 kW. Part (c) shows the irradiance, with a maximum of around 1,000 W/m². Finally, part (e) shows the outside temperature and the module temperature. The measurements of the AC part are similar to those of DC, showing in part (a) the voltages, with values

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around 240 VAC, in part (b) the current with values close to 9 AAC, with lower values on the grid side, and part (c) the AC power, also with lower values on the grid side.

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Fig. 9. DC data measured on 2024/07/07. (a) voltage; (b) current; (c) power; (d) irradiance; (e) temperatures.

Fig. 10. AC data measured on 2024/07/07. (a) voltage; (b) current; (c) power.

5.3 Data visualization

A Dashboard has been created to monitor the inverter data as well as the LoRa grid parameters. The data is refreshed every 10 seconds and the display range is 1 day. The dashboard has been realized in Node-Red. Fig. 11 shows the inverter dashboard and Fig. 12 the LoRa network dashboard.

Fig. 11. Measurement devices Dashboard created in Node-Red.

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Fig. 12. Dashboard for LoRa network data created in Node-Red.

On the other hand, an app for mobile devices has also been developed for real-time visualisation of the data generated. The application is made in MIT App Inventor for the Android operating system. Fig. 13 shows a screenshot of the application.

Fig. 13. App for display on Android devices.

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